

**FirESmart - Nature-based solutions for
preventive fire management and
sustained supply of ecosystem services**

FIRES**MART**

Project reference
PCIF/MOG/0083/2017

Final Report 28.04.2023

FIRE-SMART PROJECT

Nature-based solutions for
preventive fire management and
sustainable supply of ecosystem
services

FINAL REPORT

Recommended citation: Regos A, Campos JC, Lecina-Diaz J, Pais, S, Sil Â, Cánibe M, Freitas TR, Rodriguez S, Aquilué N, Gonçalves J, Carvalho-Santos C, Lomba Â, Moreira F, Duane A, Hermoso V, Brotons LI, Chas-Amil M, Touza J, Santos JA, Fernandes P, Azevedo J & Honrado J P. (2023). The FirESmart project – Nature-based solutions for preventive fire management and sustained supply of ecosystem services. Final Report – Project Deliverable R03. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7517623>

Photos: João Gonçalves & Silvana Pais.

Diagrams: Judit Lecina.

Project consortium: Research Center in Biodiversity and Genetic Resources of the Network in Biodiversity and Evolutionary Biology (CIBIO/InBIO); The Centre for the Research and Technology of Agro-Environmental and Biological Sciences of the University of Trás-os-Montes and Alto Douro (CITAB/UTAD); Mountain Research Centre of the Polytechnic Institute of Bragança (CIMO/IPB); Forest Sciences Centre of Catalonia - CTFC, Spain; University of Santiago de Compostela (USC); University of York.

Website: <https://firesmartproject.wordpress.com>

This research project was funded by national funds through the FCT – Foundation for Science and Technology, I.P., under the FirESmart project (PCIF/MOG/0083/2017).

Task development and accomplishment

The main research activities were developed following the work plan defined in the project proposal, structured in six work packages (WPs):

WP 1 – SET-UP OF THE MODELLING AND SIMULATION FRAMEWORK

Following Task 1.1 and 1.2, the CIBIO/InBIO team developed the REMAINS model, a **spatially explicit process-based model** to investigate how the spatiotemporal interactions between fire-vegetation dynamics, fire management and land-use changes affect fire regime at short- and medium-timescales. The model **simulates wildfires** (including fire ignition, spread, burning and two types of fire-suppression strategies) and **vegetation dynamics** (i.e., natural succession and post-fire regeneration) (Task 1.1) together with **land-use changes** (e.g., agriculture abandonment or intensification) (Task 1.2) (Fig. 1; details can be found in Pais et al., 2020). REMAINS is being recently migrated to an R environment to provide academics with unique tool to explore the spatial interactions between fire disturbance and vegetation dynamics under a wide range of fire-suppression and land-use policy scenarios (**it is freely available at [GitHub](#)**).

Fig. 1.1. Processes implemented in the REMAINS model. The model was calibrated and validated for the Biosphere Reserve Gerês-Xurés.

In addition, the UTAD team also calibrated the BFOLDS Fire Regime Module to support the assessment of fire-related functions and services in the Meseta Iberica. Based on model outputs, we assessed the landscape fire regulation capacity over time and its implications for supporting the climate regulation ecosystem service (Sil et al., 2022) (Fig. 1.2). Finally, we quantified the effect of climate change on fire danger (components of the Canadian FWI System) and wildfire behavior characteristics (rate of spread and fireline intensity) for the four major Mediterranean forest ecosystems located in the Transboundary Biosphere Reserve of Meseta Ibérica under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios. The effect of climate change on wildfire behavior was supplemented by taking into account net primary production, hence fuel load (Aparício et al., 2022).

Fig. 1.2. Diagram of the modelling workflow applied to test BFOLDS-FRM and to assess ecological functions and services related to fire and climate.

WP 2 – SCENARIO STORYLINES AND IMPLEMENTATION

WP 2 aimed to identify ‘fire-smart’ strategies and climate change scenarios, and implement scenario storylines into the modelling platforms (developed in WP1). In task 2.1., the UTAD team developed climate model datasets (comprising three main variables – daily total precipitation, maximum and minimum temperatures) for the Iberian Peninsula and the Transboundary Biosphere Reserve of Meseta Ibérica. The climate model simulations were provided for one historical period (daily data from 1989 to 2005) in the Iberian Peninsula (at 9×9 km) and two periods (daily data from 1989 to 2005 and from 2021 to 2050) in the Meseta Ibérica and Gerês-Xurés (at 1×1 km). Future climate data are available from four Global-Regional Climate Model chains and two Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP 4.5 and 8.5) (details in Campos et al., 2021) [27-Gb dataset freely available at <https://zenodo.org/record/4590027#.ZDUjbS8IP0o>].

In Task 2.2, we considered the organization of a workshop involving local stakeholders in storylines description and scenarios design of plausible fire and land-use management to be implemented in our study areas. Due to the COVID-19 outbreak, we could not organize the workshop. Instead, we sent a structured online questionnaire to more than 300 stakeholders of the two transboundary biosphere reserves. To our knowledge, this is the first study about stakeholders’ perspective regarding Nature-based Solutions (NbS) to extreme wildfires using the IUCN standards. This study is a first-step analysis representing a base for future co-design and implementation of NbS to large wildfires, contributing to the understanding of

the stakeholder support for their application in addressing the socioeconomic challenges in high fire-risk areas (see Lecina-Diaz et al., 2023; Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Percentage of answers from the study areas: Gerês- Xurés, Meseta Ibérica, and whole region (referring to respondents not directly related with the two study areas but influential in the region) and sectors (forest actors and civil protection, government, local development, nature conservation, research, and other).

WP 3 – IMPACTS OF FIRE-SMART MANAGEMENT SCENARIOS ON FIRE MITIGATION

Using the modelling platform developed in WP1, fire and landscape will be simulated under each fire-smart management scenario (see Table 1, extracted from Pais et al., 2020) according to the storylines defined and implemented in WP2 (Task 3.1). WP3 aimed to predict potential impacts of the ‘fire-smart’ management strategies identified in WP2 on fire regime, and quantify the economic costs of each strategy through a cost-benefit analysis (Task 3.2; Fig. 3) (Lecina-Diaz et al., 2023b; Pais et al., 2020).

Table 1
Landscape and fire management storylines for the study area.

Name	Storyline description
Business-as-usual – BAU	It envisages a future landscape derived from the historical fire regime and land-use change trends reported between 1987 and 2010, clearly dominated by land abandonment processes (Regos et al., 2015).
High Nature Value farmlands – HNVf	Related to initiatives aimed at reverting farmland abandonment and mimicking EU environmental and rural policies on fire regime and biodiversity conservation (Lomba et al., 2015; Moreira and Pe'er, 2018) in the BR-GX as a counterpoint of the current BAU scenario.
Fire-Smart	It aims at controlling final burnt area by intervening on vegetation covers (e.g. promoting the gradual conversions of coniferous forests to native oak woodlands) to foster more fire-resistant (less flammable) and/or fire-resilient landscapes (Fernandes, 2013). Assuming the same amount of fire suppression resources applied nowadays, a more effective fire-suppression system would be expected due to lower fire spread rates found in oaks than in coniferous forests (Fernandes, 2013).
HNVf + Fire Smart	It envisages an integrated management policy that combines the promotion of more resistant and less flammable landscapes (‘Fire-smart’) with policies aimed at gradually increasing agricultural areas (HNVf), as an opportunity for fire suppression and farmland/grassland biodiversity conservation.

Fig. 3. Wildfire suppression costs and net suppression costs under land-use management scenarios.

WP4 – IMPACTS OF FIRE-SMART MANAGEMENT SCENARIOS ON ECOSYSTEMS SERVICES

WP4 aimed to predict impacts of the ‘fire-smart’ management strategies identified in WP2 on biodiversity and ecosystem services. In Task 4.1, different ecosystem services (climate regulation, recreation, wood and food production) were modeled under each management scenario [see (Cánibe et al., 2022; Lecina-Díaz et al., 2023b)]. In Task 4.2, we predicted environmental suitability changes for more than 100 vertebrate species by using a species distribution modelling framework that hierarchically integrated global climate change (RCP 4.5 and 8.5 scenarios) and regional land-use and fire suppression management scenarios.

- 1) Model simulations reveals how an effective implementation of extensive agricultural policies (supporting **High Nature Value farmlands**) would reduce fire hazard while simultaneously ensuring biodiversity conservation. The results suggest that, although **‘fire-smart’ forest conversion strategies** would be beneficial for climate regulation ecosystem services (measured through carbon sequestration rates), their implementation **should be integrated into the EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) to jointly reduce fire hazard and conserve local biodiversity** (Pais et al., 2020).
- 2) Although ‘HNVP’ was found to be the best scenario, **using fire to enhance rewilding may provide a nature-based solution when societal support through agricultural policies fails** (Campos et al., 2020).
- 3) In addition, the European Union, following the Green Deal roadmap towards a decarbonization of the economy, has committed to ambitious habitat restoration goals in particular those with the most potential to capture and store carbon. These include planting three billion trees by 2030 in its recently adopted Biodiversity Strategy. However, these ‘climate-smart’ policies entail important challenges associated with fire risk, being a commonly overlooked risk, that needs to be carefully evaluated when deciding where and how to restore forests across Europe (Hermoso et al., 2021). Fire-smart scenarios (‘Farmland recovery’, ‘Agroforestry recovery’) also benefit carbon regulation services. In fact, climate- and fire-smart policies can help develop multifunctional landscapes that help mitigate and adapt to climate change and ensure the best possible maintenance of biodiversity and ecosystem services under uncertain future climate conditions (Campos et al., 2022; Cánibe et al., 2022).
- 4) However, we would need a redesign and expansion of the ‘core’ protected areas to mitigate changes in biodiversity and accommodate ecosystem services under expected changes in climate and species distribution (Cánibe et al., 2022) (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Scenario implemented in the Biosphere Reserve ‘Meseta Ibérica’. Zonation suggested from MARXAN simulations under each scenario and trade-offs between food provisioning, climate regulation, soil erosion control and recreation.

WP5 –TRADE-OFFS AND ‘WIN-WIN’ SOLUTIONS BETWEEN FIRE MITIGATION AND ECOSYSTEM SERVICES: SYNTHESIS

In Task 5.1., our team investigated synergies and trade-offs between benefits obtained from different ecosystem services derived under alternative fire management scenarios. We applied the least-cost-plus-net-value-change approach and estimated net changes in wildfire damages based on their implications for the 2010–2050 period and five ecosystem services: agriculture, pasture, timber, recreation and climate regulation (see Fig. 5 and Lecina-Diaz et al., 2023c).

Figure 5. Bar plots of a) damages; b) avoided damages; and c) net value change (damages - avoided damages) for each ecosystem service (food provision, pasture provision, timber provision, recreation and climate regulation) over the 2010–2050 period under the different scenarios.

WP6 - DISSEMINATION AND TRANSFER KNOWLEDGE PLANS

The **dissemination and transfer of knowledge material** created in the context of the **FirESmart** constituted a fundamental piece of this research project. The project outcomes were published in prestigious journals (see [outputs](#)). Our team has so far published **19 scientific publications in top-ranking journals** such as *Nature*, *Science*, *Global Change Biology*, *Science of Total Environment* or *Frontiers in Ecology and Environment*. The project has been well accepted by **local stakeholders**, having a great media impact at Iberian Peninsula level (see [dissemination](#)). Project results were presented in several **national and international conferences** (Portugal, Spain, Italia, France and Estonia, and USA, see [conferences subsection](#)). To ensure an uptake of the project recommendations by policymakers, we have designed an **outreach video** (with more than 500 views) and a policy brief (freely available [at Zenodo](#)). I would remark that the last Spanish [WWF](#)¹ and French IUCN² reports (*Nature-based Solutions for Gravity and Fire Risks in France*) were based upon results of the FirESmart project. Finally, I would mention a couple of letters *Correspondence* sent to *Nature* last year, where we briefly outline challenges and opportunities for policymaking that will arise from EU Green Deal, being a roadmap for my future research on wildfire prevention [Regos A (2022). [Nature-based solutions in an era of mega-fires](#). *Nature* 607, (7919) 449-449; Fernandes PM (2022). [Make Europe's forests climate-smart and fire-smart](#). *Nature* 609, 32 DOI: [10.1038/d41586-022-02318-2](#)].

References

- Aparício, B.A., Santos, J.A., Freitas, T.R., Sá, A.C.L., Pereira, J.M.C., Fernandes, P.M., 2022. Unravelling the effect of climate change on fire danger and fire behaviour in the Transboundary Biosphere Reserve of Meseta Ibérica (Portugal-Spain). *Clim. Change* 173, 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-022-03399-8>
- Campos, J.C., Bernhardt, J., Aquilué, N., Brotons, L., Domínguez, J., Lomba, Â., Marcos, B., Martínez-freiría, F., Moreira, F., Pais, S., Honrado, J.P., Regos, A., 2020. Using fire to enhance rewilding when agricultural policies fail. *Sci. Total Environ.* 142897. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.142897>
- Campos, J.C., Rodrigues, S., Freitas, T., Santos, J.A., Honrado, J.P., 2021. Climatic variables and ecological modelling data for birds, amphibians and reptiles in the Transboundary Biosphere Reserve of Meseta Ibérica (Portugal-Spain). *Biodivers. Data J.* 9, e66509. <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.9.e66509>
- Campos, J.C., Rodrigues, S., Sil, Â., Hermoso, V., Freitas, T., Santos, J., Fernandes, P.M., Azevedo, J.C., Honrado, J.P., Regos, A., 2022. Climate regulation ecosystem services and biodiversity conservation are enhanced differently by climate- and fire-smart landscape management. *Environ. Res. Lett.*
- Cánibe, M., Hermoso, V., Campos, J., Carvalho-Santos, C., Fernandes, P.M., Freitas, T.R., Honrado, J.P., Santos, J.A., Sil, Â., Regos, A., Azevedo, J.C., 2022. Climate and fire-smart landscape scenarios call for redesigning protection regimes to achieve multiple management goals. *J. Environ. Manage.* 322, 116045.
- Hermoso, V., Regos, A., Morán-Ordóñez, A., Duane, A., Brotons, L., 2021. Tree-planting: a double-edged sword to fight climate change in an era of megafires. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 27, 3001–3003. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15625>
- Lecina-Díaz, J., Campos, J.C., Pais, S., Carvalho-Santos, C., Azevedo, J.C., Fernandes, P.M., João, G., Aquilué, N., Rocés-Díaz, J. V., Agrelo de la Torre, M., Brotons, L., Chas-

¹ Worldwide Fund for Nature Inc (WWF)

² The International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)

- Amil, M.L., Lomba, A., Duane, A., Moreira, F., Touza, J.M., Hermoso, V., Vicente, J.R., Honrado, J.P., Regos, A., 2023a. Stakeholder perceptions of wildfire management strategies as nature-based solutions in two Iberian biosphere reserves. *Ecol. Soc.* 28, 39.
- Lecina-Diaz, J., Chas-Amil, M.-L., Aquilué, N., Sil, Â., Brotons, L., Regos, A., Touza, J., 2023b. Incorporating fire-smartness into agricultural policies minimises suppression costs and ecosystem services damages from wildfires. *J. Environ. Manage.* 2023.01.20.524753. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2023.117707>
- Lecina-Diaz, J., Chas-Amil, M.-L., Aquilué, N., Sil, Â., Brotons, L., Regos, A., Touza, J., 2023c. Incorporating fire-smartness into agricultural policies minimises suppression costs and ecosystem services damages from wildfires. *J. Environ. Manage.* 337, 117707. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2023.117707>
- Pais, S., Aquilué, N., Campos, J., Sil, Â., Marcos, B., Martínez-freiría, F., Domínguez, J., Brotons, L., Honrado, J.P., Regos, A., 2020. Mountain farmland protection and fire-smart management jointly reduce fire hazard and enhance biodiversity and carbon sequestration. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 44, 101143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2020.101143>
- Sil, Â., Azevedo, J.C., Fernandes, P.M., Alonso, J., Honrado, J.P., 2022. Fine-tuning the BFOLDS Fire Regime Module to support the assessment of fire-related functions and services in a changing Mediterranean mountain landscape. *Environ. Model. Softw.* 155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2022.105464>

Contingency plan

Overall, the project was developed following the work plan and timetable. Nevertheless, the Workshops initially planned were replaced by on-line questionnaires in order to deal with the personal meeting constraints that came up due to the COVID-19. These questionnaires were sent to more than 300 stakeholders of the two transboundary biosphere reserves. We got answers from more than 100 stakeholders that allows to carefully analyze their perspective. To our knowledge, this is the first study about stakeholders' perspective regarding Nature-based Solutions (NbS) to extreme wildfires using the IUCN standards. This study is a first-step analysis representing a base for future co-design and implementation of NbS to large wildfires, contributing to the understanding of the stakeholder support for their application in addressing the socioeconomic challenges in high fire-risk areas. Personally, I think that this alternative offered us a much better perspective and complete information across multiple sectors involved in the wildfire problem. In addition, the in-person meeting required to coordinate the different research activities within the team were substituted by on-line meetings by using different platform such as Teams or Zoom. These technologies allowed us to keep working properly in the different task with no important impacts on project milestones, research activities or scheduled work plan. The commitment of the team members, but very especially the hired post-doc and technicians, was essential to on-time delivery of the main research outcomes.

The COVID outbreak had also impacts in terms in the time needed to publish some of the research studies. The availability of reviewers was largely affected by COVID situation, which led to important delays in the peer-review process. In this regard, the flexibility of the FCT allows to have enough time (up to an additional year) to publish most of 'core papers', which in turn made possible the dissemination of the main findings on time. Still, the last of two papers were published when the project was ended, which prevent us from using the remaining budget (round 7,000 euros) to pay the open access fees. I would remark that the

editorial office of the *International Journal of Wildland Fire* will publish the last paper in open access without paying, a very kind and unusual response to our situation. It was not the case for the study published in *Journal of Environmental Management* (Elsevier), being funded by the internal budget of the host institution (CIBIO).

I would also like to mention a last issue, related with the difficulties of finding postdoc fellows given the FCT limitation of 3 years after PhD defense. The improvement of the post-doc position from fellowships to contracts is a firm step forward and very positive, but it should be supported by an increase in the budget of the FCT projects in order to ensure our capacity to successfully develop the scientific advances of our future projects. The condition of being formally in PhD programs for the BI (bolseiros de investigação) constrained the number of candidates that can apply to these calls.

Budget balance and relocation

The abovementioned difficulties were successfully surpassed but no without a slight reorganization of the budget. Basically, part of the budget initially destined to internal meetings and workshops was relocated to human resources, which allowed to extend the contract of the Dr. João Campos from initial 17 to 24 months. The second post-doc, Dra. Judit Lecina was hired by another institution in Germany after the first 12-months with us. We asked permission to the FCT to destinate the remaining budget (equivalent to 5 months) to the first post-doc contract. The flexibility of the FCT was critical to overcome these unexpected situations.

Expected output indicators

SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

19. Regos A, Pais S, Campos JC, Lecina-Díaz J (2023). **Nature-based solutions to wildfires in rural landscapes of Southern Europe: let's be fire-smart!** *International Journal of Wildland Fire* (*in press*) .
18. Lecina-Díaz J, Chas-Amil ML, Aquilué N, Sil Â, Brotons Ll, Regos A & Touza J (2023). **Incorporating fire-smartness into agricultural policies reduces suppression costs and ecosystem services damages from wildfires.** *Journal of Environmental Management* 337: 117707. DOI: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2023.117707.
17. Lecina-Díaz J, Campos JC, Pais S, Carvalho-Santos C, Azevedo JC, Fernandes P, Gonçalves JF, Aquilué N, Rocés-Díaz J, Agrelo de la Torre M, Brotons Ll, Chas-Amil ML, Lomba Â, Duane A, Moreira F, Touza J, Hermoso V, Sil Â, Vicente J, Honrado J & Regos A (2023). **Stakeholder perceptions of wildfire management strategies as Nature-based solutions in two Iberian Biosphere Reserves.** *Ecology & Society* 28 (1): 39. DOI:10.5751/ES-13907-280139.
16. Cánibe M, Hermoso V, Campos JC, Carvalho-Santos C, Fernandes P, Freitas TR, Honrado JP, Santos JA, Sil Â, Regos A & Azevedo J (2022). **Climate- and fire-smart landscape scenarios call for redesigning protection regimes to achieve multiple management goals.** *Journal of Environmental Management* 322: 116045. DOI: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.116045
15. Fernandes PM (2022). **Make Europe's forests climate-smart and fire-smart.** *Nature* 609, 32 DOI: 10.1038/d41586-022-02318-2.

14. Regos A (2022). **Nature-based solutions in an era of mega-fires.** *Nature* 607, 449. DOI:10.1038/d41586-022-01955-x.
13. Sil A, Azevedo JC, Fernandes PM, Alonso J & Honrado JP (2022). **Fine-tuning the BFOLDS Fire Regime Module to support the assessment of fire-related functions and services in a changing Mediterranean mountain landscape.** *Environmental Modelling & Software.* 155, 105464. DOI:10.1016/j.envsoft.2022.105464
12. Aparício BA, Santos JA, Freitas TR, Sá ACL, Pereira JMC, Fernandes PM (2022). **Unravelling the effect of climate change on fire danger and fire behaviour in the Transboundary Biosphere Reserve of Meseta Ibérica (Portugal-Spain).** *Climatic Change* 173, 5. DOI:10.1007/s10584-022-03399-8.
11. Linley GD, Jolly CJ, Doherty TS, Geary WL, Armenteras-Pascual D, Belcher C, Bliege BR, Duane A, Fletcher M-S, Giorgis M A, Angie H, Jones GM, Kelly LT, Lee CKF, Nolan R H, Parr CL, Pausas J, Price JN, Regos A, Ritchie EG, Ruffault J, Williamson GJ. Wu Q & Nimmo DG (2022). **What do you mean, ‘megafire’?** *Global Ecology and Biogeography* 31:1906–1922. DOI: 10.1111/geb.13499.
10. Campos JC, Rodrigues S, Sil Â, Hermoso V, Freitas T, Santos JA, Fernandes PM, Azevedo JC, Honrado JP and Regos A (2022). **Climate regulation ecosystem services and biodiversity conservation are enhanced differently by climate- and fire-smart landscape management.** *Environmental Research Letters*, 17 (5): 054014 DOI:10.1088/1748-9326/ac64b5.
9. Lanzas M, Hermoso V, Morán-Ordóñez A, Regos A, Bota G and Brotons L (2021). **The value of unprotected land for future conservation efforts under dynamic conditions.** *Biological Conservation*, 261, 109232. DOI:10.1016/j.biocon.2021.109232.
8. Campos JC, Rodrigues S, Freitas T, Santos JA, Honrado JP and Regos A (2021). **Climatic variables and ecological modelling data for birds, amphibians and reptiles in the Transboundary Biosphere Reserve of Meseta Ibérica (Portugal-Spain).** *Biodiversity Data Journal*, 9: e66509. DOI:10.3897/BDJ.9.e66509.
7. Hermoso V, Regos A, Morán-Ordóñez A, Duane A and Brotons L (2021). **Tree-planting: a double-edged sword to fight climate change in an era of megafires.** *Global Change Biology*. 27:3001–3003. DOI:10.1111/gcb.15625.
6. Kelly LT, Giljohann KM, Duane A, Aquilué N, Archibald S, Batllori E, Bennett AF, Buckland ST, Canelles Q, Clarke MF, Fortin M-J, Hermoso V, Herrando S, Keane RE, Lake FK, McCarthy MA, Ordóñez AM, Parr CL, Pausas JG, Penman TD, Regos A, Rumpff L, Santos JL, Smith AL, Syphard AD, Tingley MW and Brotons L (2020). **Fire and biodiversity in the Anthropocene.** *Science*, 370, eabb0355. DOI:10.1126/science.abb0355.
5. Campos JC, Bernhardt J, Aquilué N, Brotons L, Domínguez J, Lomba Â, Marcos B, Martínez-Freiría F, Moreira F, Pais S, Honrado JP and Regos A (2020). **Using fire to enhance rewilding when agricultural policies fail.** *Science of the Total Environment*, 755, 142897. DOI:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.142897.
4. Pais S, Aquilué N, Campos J, Sil Â, Marcos B, Martínez-Freiría F, Domínguez J, Brotons L, Honrado JP and Regos A (2020). **Mountain farmland protection and fire-smart management jointly reduce fire hazard and enhance biodiversity and carbon sequestration.** *Ecosystem Services*, 44: 101143. DOI:10.1016/j.ecoser.2020.101143.

3. Moreira F, Ascoli D, Safford H, Adams MA, Moreno JM, Pereira JMC, Catry FX, Armesto J, Bond W, González ME, Curt T, Koutsias N, McCaw L, Price O, Pausas JG, Rigolot E, Stephens S, Tavsanoglu C, Vallejo VR, Van Wilgen BW, Xanthopoulos G and Fernandes PM (2020). **Wildfire management in Mediterranean-type regions: paradigm change needed.** *Environmental Research Letters*, 15(1): 011001. DOI:10.1088/1748-9326/ab541e.

2. Carvalho-Santos C, Marcos B, Nunes JP, Regos A, Palazzi E, Terzago S, Monteiro AT and Honrado JP (2019). **Hydrological Impacts of Large Fires and Future Climate: Modeling Approach Supported by Satellite Data.** *Remote Sensing*, 11 (23): 2832. DOI:10.3390/rs11232832.

1. Sil A, Azevedo JC, Fernandes PM, Regos A, Vaz AS and Honrado JP (2019). **(Wild)fire is not an ecosystem service.** *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 17 (8): 429-430. DOI:10.1002/fee.2106.

DATA PUBLICATIONS

2. Campos JC, Rodrigues S, Freitas T, Santos JA, Honrado JP and Regos A (2021). **Climate models (Part 1) for the Iberian Peninsula and the Transboundary Biosphere Reserve of Meseta Ibérica (Portugal-Spain) [Data set].** *Zenodo*. DOI:10.5281/zenodo.4589376.

1. Campos JC, Rodrigues S, Freitas T, Santos JA, Honrado JP and Regos A (2021). **Species distribution models (Part 2) for birds, amphibians and reptiles in the Transboundary Biosphere Reserve of Meseta Ibérica (Portugal-Spain) [Data set].** *Zenodo*. DOI:10.5281/zenodo.4599822.

SPECIAL ISSUES

2. Regos, A (2022). Special Issue “**Nature-based Solutions to Extreme Wildfires**” *Fire* (ISSN 2571-6255). This special issue belongs to the section “Fire Research at the Science–Policy–Practitioner Interface”.

1. Touza J, Prestemon J, Chas-Amil M, Butry D (2021) Special Issue “**Building Wildfire Disaster Resilience and Climate Change Adaptation**” *Sustainability*(ISSN 2071-1050).

CONFERENCES, SYMPOSIUMS AND WORKSHOPS

26. Regos A. **From local stakeholders to policy recommendations: a synthesis of the FirESmart project.** Closing Seminar – Eco.Fire project. January 13, 2023 Online event.

25. Pais, S.; Campos, J. C.; Lecina-Diaz, J.; Regos, A (2022). **Fire-smart management as nature-based solution to extreme wildfires in abandoned rural landscapes of Southern Europe.** In Book: Advances in Forest Fire Research 2022; D. X. Viegas & L.M. Ribeiro, Ed.; Chapter 6 – Wildfire Management and safety; pp. 1634–1639. DOI: 10.14195/978-989-26-2298-9_250.

24. Regos A (2022). **Mainstreaming ‘fire-smart’ management in land-use policies to support the transition towards more resilient landscapes: challenges and opportunities.** Fire Ecology Across Boundaries: Connecting Science and Management. October 4-7 Florence (Italy).

23. Sil Â, Azevedo JC, Fernandes PM, Regos A, Campos J, Santos JA, Freitas T & Honrado JP (2022). **Comparing the effect of fire management strategies on fire regulation capacity in a Mediterranean mountainous landscape undergoing farmland abandonment and climate change.** IALE 2022 European Landscape Ecology Congress Jul 11 – 15, 2022. Warsaw, Poland (Online).
22. Cánibe M, Campos JC, Carvalho-Santos C, Hermoso V, Regos A, Sil Â & Azevedo JC (2022). **Coping with fire in a Mediterranean biosphere reserve: a multiobjective plan under uncertain future global change** IALE 2022 European Landscape Ecology Congress Jul 11 – 15, 2022. Warsaw, Poland (Online).
21. Regos A (2022). **Wildfire scenarios and ecosystem services integration in fire risk reduction.** FIRE-RES technical workshop: “Towards fire resilient landscapes in Europe”. 14 – 15th of June 2022. Solsona (Catalonia, Spain).
20. Regos A, Aguiar C, Lopes D. (2022). **Floresta, fogo, animais e pessoas: a complexa equação da sustentabilidade nos territórios de montanha.** DIVERSIDADES: Ciclos de conversas sobre a biodiversidade e sustentabilidade ambiental. 5 de maio de 2022, 21h30 – 23h00 | Online.
19. Regos A (2022). **Les SfN pour la gestion préventive des incendies de forêt et la fourniture durable de services écosystémiques.** *Forum Life ARTISAN, 15 Mars 2022, ATELIER N°2, Lille, France.* (<https://www.yuca.tv/fr/ofb/forum-artisan-15-03-22-atelier2-11h30>).
18. Regos A, Campos JC, Bernhardt J, Aquilué N, Brotons L, Domínguez J, Lomba Â, Marcos B, Martínez-Freiría F, Moreira F, Pais S, Honrado JP (2021). **Using fire to enhance rewilding when agricultural policies fail.** *Symposium: Actions for sustaining biodiversity in fire-prone ecosystems. 9th International Fire Ecology and Management Congress.* November 30 – December 3.
17. Adrián Regos – **Participation in the organization of the XV Congreso Nacional de la Asociación Española de Ecología Terrestre (AEET). 18-21 October 2021, Plasencia, Cáceres – Spain.**
16. Campos JC, Bernhardt J, Aquilué N, Brotons L, Domínguez J, Lomba Â, Marcos B, Martínez-Freiría F, Moreira F, Pais S, Honrado JP and Regos A (2021). **Fire as a tool to enhance rewilding in the abandoned rural mountains of the Gerês-Xurés.** *XV Congreso Nacional de la Asociación Española de Ecología Terrestre (AEET). 18-21 October, Plasencia, Cáceres – Spain.*
15. Adrián Regos and Judit Lecina-Díaz – **Participation in the organization of the 3rd Ecosystem Services Partnership (ESP) Europe Conference. 7-10 June 2021, Tartu, Estonia.**
14. Lecina-Díaz J, Campos J, Gonçalves J, Carvalho-Santos C, Agrelo M, Aquilué N, Azevedo J, Brotons L, Chas-Amil M, Alves Cordeiro Rodrigues S, Duane A, Fernandes P, Hermoso V, Lomba A, Macedo de Freitas T, Moreira F, Pais S, Rocés-Díaz J, Santos J, Sil Â, Touza-Montero J, Vicente J, Honrado J and Regos A (2021). **Nature-based solutions to wildfires in complex socioecological systems: insights from stakeholders’ perspectives in two transboundary protected areas.** *3rd Ecosystem Services Partnership (ESP) Europe Conference. 7-10 June, Tartu, Estonia.*

13. Sil Â, Fernandes PM, Honrado JP and Azevedo JC (2021). **Evaluation and application of a fire regime modelling tool to characterize fire-related functions and services in a fire-prone Mediterranean mountain landscape.** *3rd Ecosystem Services Partnership (ESP) Europe Conference. 7-10 June, Tartu, Estonia.*
12. Campos JC, Rodrigues S, Sil Â, Hermoso V, Freitas TR, Santos JA, Fernandes PM, Azevedo JC, Honrado JP and Regos A (2021). **Trade-offs between climate regulation and biodiversity conservation under climate- and fire-smart land management policies.** *3rd Ecosystem Services Partnership (ESP) Europe Conference. 7-10 June, Tartu, Estonia.*
11. Campos JC (2021). **Soluções baseadas na natureza para a gestão preventiva do risco de incêndios e fornecimento sustentado de serviços dos ecossistemas.** *2º Workshop de Projetos de Investigação científica e desenvolvimento tecnológico no âmbito da prevenção e combate a incêndios florestais. 30 de Abril de 2021.*
10. Pais S, Aquilué N, Campos JC, Sil Â, Marcos B, Martínez-Freiría F, Domínguez J, Brotons L, Honrado JP and Regos A (2020). **A promoção de paisagens Fire-Smart como solução sustentável aos grandes incêndios florestais em áreas montanhosas afetadas pelo abandono rural e mudança climática.** *XIX Encontro Nacional de Ecologia – Sociedade Portuguesa de Ecologia (SPECO). 9-12 de Dezembro 2020.*
9. Campos JC, Bernhardt J, Aquilué N, Brotons L, Domínguez J, Lomba Â, Marcos B, Martínez-Freiría F, Moreira F, Pais S, Honrado JP and Regos A (2020). **O fogo como ferramenta para potenciar o Rewilding em áreas de montanha abandonadas.** *XIX Encontro Nacional de Ecologia – Sociedade Portuguesa de Ecologia (SPECO). 9-12 de Dezembro 2020.*
8. Regos A (2020). **FirESmart project – seeking nature-based solutions for preventive fire management and sustainable supply of ecosystem services.** *1º Workshop de Projetos de Investigação científica e desenvolvimento tecnológico no âmbito da prevenção e combate a incêndios florestais. Coimbra, 14 de Fevereiro 2020.*
7. Regos A (2019). **O projeto FirESmart: Soluções baseadas na natureza para a gestão preventiva do risco de incêndios e fornecimento sustentado de serviços dos ecossistemas.** *Incêndios Rurais: gestão com base em evidência científica. Lisboa, 27 de Novembro 2019.*
6. Regos A, Aquilué N, Azevedo JC, Brotons L, Campos JC, Carvalho-Santos C, et al. (2019). **FirESmart – Nature-based solutions for preventive fire management and sustained supply of ecosystem services.** *Incêndios Rurais: gestão com base em evidência científica. Lisboa, 27 de Novembro 2019.*
5. Fernandes P (2019). **Paisagens florestais resilientes ao fogo em Portugal: Opções e evidências. Seminário Paisagens Fire-smart.** *Criando territórios resilientes ao fogo. Castrelo Branco, 8 de Novembro 2019.*
4. Pais S, Aquilué N, Brotons L, Domínguez J, Honrado JP and Regos A (2019). **Cenários de gestão fire-smart da paisagem: impactes sobre o regime de fogo e a conservação da biodiversidade numa área protegida transfronteiriça.** *Seminário Paisagens Fire-smart. Criando territórios resilientes ao fogo. Castrelo Branco, 8 de Novembro 2019.*
3. Regos A, Aquilué N, Pais S, Sil Â, Marcos B, Brotons L and Honrado JP (2019). **Fire-landscape dynamic model to assess future trade-offs between preventive fire management, nature conservation and sustained supply of ecosystem services.** *The*

International Society for Ecological Modelling Global Conference 2019 (ISEM2019). October 1-5. Salzburg, Austria.

2. Pais S, Aquilué N, Brotons L, Domínguez J, Honrado JP and Regos A (2019). **Trade-offs between fire prevention and bird conservation under fire-smart landscape management scenarios.** *Embedding Ecology in Sustainable Development Goals, EEF 2019 | 15th EEF – European Ecological Federation Congress. July 29 – August 2, 2019. Lisbon, Portugal.*

1. Carvalho-Santo C, Marcos B, Regos A, Nunes JP, Palazzi E, Terzago S, Monteiro A and Honrado JP (2019). **Hydrological impacts of large fires and climate change: modelling approach using SWAT and satellite data.** *Embedding Ecology in Sustainable Development Goals, EEF 2019 | 15th EEF – European Ecological Federation Congress. July 29 – August 2, 2019. Lisbon, Portugal.*

MASTER THESES

3. Lamas da Costa J (2022). ***A influência das paisagens resilientes ao fogo na disponibilidade hídrica e no controlo da erosão do solo: lições para a Reserva da Biosfera Transfronteiriça Meseta Ibérica.*** MSc Thesis. University of Porto. Supervisor: Claudia Carvalho-Santos. Co-supervisor: Adrián Regos.

2. Rodrigues S (2020). ***Future impacts of fire-smart landscape management on biodiversity under rural abandonment and climate change scenarios.*** MSc Thesis. University of Porto. Supervisor: Adrián Regos; co-supervisors: João P. Honrado, João Campos.

1. Pais S (2019). ***Cenários de gestão fire-smart da paisagem: impactos sobre o regime de fogo e a conservação da biodiversidade numa área protegida transfronteiriça.*** MSc Thesis. University of Porto. Supervisor: Adrián Regos; co-supervisor: João P. Honrado.